

ENHANCING ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AND ENGAGEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION PHYSICS USING ALGODOO SIMULATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Algodoo is a 2D physics simulation software used to visualize physics concepts. This study examined the impact of Algodoo simulations on academic performance, retention, and engagement in a Wave and Optics course at Bukidnon State University during the first semester of SY 2024–2025. Using a quasi-experimental design, 37 students were divided into two groups: one used Algodoo simulations and the other used traditional Laboratory Optics Kits. Academic performance was measured through pretests, posttests, and retention tests, while student engagement was assessed across cognitive, behavioral, and affective domains using a validated questionnaire. Findings revealed that both instructional methods led to the improvement of academic performance. Although posttest results showed no statistically significant difference between groups, retention scores were significantly higher in the Algodoo group, indicating better long-term learning. Engagement increased significantly in both groups across all domains, with the non-Algodoo group showing slightly higher behavioral and affective engagement, though the differences were not statistically significant. Overall, the study suggests that combining Algodoo simulations with traditional laboratory tools can enhance learning outcomes in physics education. A blended learning approach is recommended to maximize the strengths of both methods. Future research should consider larger sample sizes and explore the long-term impacts of technology-driven simulations on science education.

Keywords: *Algodoo simulations, academic performance, retention, student engagement, Traditional Laboratory Optics Kit, Wave and Optics*

INTRODUCTION

Physics is a foundational science that is the key to understanding other branches of science. However, in the Philippines, it remains one of the most challenging subjects for pre-service science teachers who will teach physics in the future. Studies have shown that this difficulty stems from its abstract nature, mathematical complexity, and the lack of concrete, relatable examples (Bugarso et al., 2024). Thus, many pre-service science teachers demonstrate low motivation and conceptual understanding of physics, lacking mastery of content and skills to deliver the subject.

Moreover, the problem is worsened by the lack of physical resources, limited numeracy skills, and scientific literacy among educators in the country (Diate & Mordeno, 2021). These challenges persist at Bukidnon State University, the study site. Ramirez (2020) observed that many pre-service teachers enter the profession with inadequate preparation, often lacking hands-on experience and mastery of subject-specific pedagogy. The lack of preparedness of our future educators could contribute to a cycle of low academic performance and Engagement in physics (Laban, 2022).

Improving the quality of physics education begins with enhancing the training and competency of pre-service teachers. Stewart et al. (2021) emphasized that equipping teacher candidates with strong content knowledge and pedagogical skills increases the likelihood of effective, student-centered instruction. As 21st-century learners thrive in collaborative and technological environments, there is a growing need to assess digital tools that complement conventional teaching strategies. Among these innovations is Algodoo, a two-dimensional simulation software designed to support the visualization of physical concepts through interactive, real-time modeling. Algodoo allows learners to explore, manipulate, and test physical phenomena in a risk-free, engaging environment.

Integrating Algodoo in physics instruction should enhance learning outcomes based on several educational theories. Rooted in Constructivist Learning Theory, Algodoo simulations encourage students to build knowledge through active, meaningful Engagement with simulations and collaboration with their peers (Piaget, 1952; Vygotsky, 1978). Dual Coding Theory further supports its use, proposing that learners retain information more effectively when it is presented through both verbal and visual modalities (Clark & Paivio, 1991). Lastly, Mayer's (2009) Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning provides a framework for effective digital instruction, such as selecting, organizing, and integrating verbal and pictorial models and topic representation, reducing cognitive load and enhancing understanding. These theories validate using simulation-based tools like Algodoo to support conceptual understanding and Engagement in complex subjects like physics.

This study compared two pedagogical methods: Algodoo simulations and

Laboratory Optics Kits. Laboratory Optics Kits and Algodoo simulations are core laboratory tools that allow learners to utilize their theoretical concepts in real-life situations. By comparing the two methods, the study will frame student preferences for the 21st century and contribute to pre-service teachers' conceptualization and pedagogy. Although several studies examined the impact of simulations on science education, less work has compared their incorporation at a university level and for pre-service teachers who will teach physics (Kefalis et al., 2025).

Overall, this research investigated the effect of Algodoo simulations on pre-service teachers' academic performance and participation in Wave and Optics. The research bridges this gap by investigating the comparison between virtual simulations and contemporary laboratory procedures in promoting conceptual understanding and active Engagement. The results of this study may reflect a pedagogy gap and the capacity of simulation-based tools to compensate for limited access to laboratories and a lack of instructional scaffolding.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of students' academic performance when exposed to Algodoo simulations and those exposed to Laboratory Optics Kits?
2. What is the level of students' engagement when exposed to Algodoo simulations and those exposed to Laboratory Optics Kits?
3. Is there a significant difference in the academic performance of students exposed to Algodoo simulations and those exposed to Laboratory Optics Kits?
4. Is there a significant difference in students' engagement between those exposed to Algodoo simulations and those exposed to Laboratory Optics Kits?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a quasi-experimental design involving two groups: one exposed to Algodoo simulations and another using Laboratory Optics Kits. Thirty-seven third-year BSEd General Science students enrolled in a Wave and Optics course were randomly assigned to the two groups based on laboratory capacity. The instructional strategy for both groups followed the 7E Learning Model to ensure consistent pedagogical approaches across interventions.

The study was conducted at Bukidnon State University, which established science programs and facilities that contain optics kits necessary for Optics concepts. To maintain ethical standards, clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Review Committee, and approval was secured from the appropriate college authorities.

Simple random sampling was used to divide students into 19 in the Algodoo group and 18 in the Laboratory Optics Kits group. Data collection tools included a 60-item academic performance test and a parallel 60-item retention test, validated by experts and pilot-tested, yielding Cronbach's alpha values of 0.832 and 0.816, respectively. Student

engagement was assessed using a 30-item Likert-type questionnaire adapted from Gaylo & Dales (2017), with high reliability (Cronbach's alpha = 0.931). This instrument measured cognitive, affective, and behavioral engagement and was validated and pilot-tested.

Students took a pretest, posttest, and retention test two weeks after the posttest. The Algodoo group implemented the simulations through a 7E lesson design, while the Laboratory Optics Kits group used conventional materials following the same instructional framework from Bukidnon State University. The teacher facilitated both groups to minimize instructor bias.

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean, percentages, and mean percentage score) and non-parametric tests such as the Mann-Whitney U test to compare academic performance and retention between groups. Engagement levels were interpreted through computed mean scores. The study's scope was limited to Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science students and Wave and Optics concepts, with no consideration for students' prior academic performance, demographic variables, and skills in the grouping process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Student's Academic Performance in Wave and Optics

Table 1 presents the academic performance levels of students exposed to two different instructional methods: Algodoo simulations and Laboratory Optics Kits using the Laboratory Optics Kits.

Table 1. Students' Academic Performance in Wave and Optics: Pretest and Posttest Results

Range of Scores	Algodoo simulations Group				Laboratory Optics Kits Group				Level of Proficiency
	Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest		
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	
59-60	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	E
55-58	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	VHS
52-54	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	3	16%	HS
49-51	0	0%	1	6%	0	0%	2	11%	S
46-48	0	0%	1	6%	0	0%	1	5%	MS
43-45	0	0%	3	17%	0	0%	1	5%	LS
41-42	0	0%	1	6%	0	0%	0	0%	BTP
40	0	0%	1	6%	0	0%	2	11%	P
31-39	0	0%	10	56%	0	0%	10	63%	BP
0-30	18	100%	1	6%	19	100%	0	0%	F
Mean	22.00		41.53		18.94		38.94		
MPS	36.67		69.22		31.57		64.90		
	(F)		(BTP)		(F)		(BP)		

Legend:

Range of Grade 59-60 Grading Scale 98-100 Level of Proficiency Excellent (E)

55-58	92-97	Very High Satisfactory (VHS)
52-54	87-91	Highly Satisfactory (HS)
49-51	82-86	Satisfactory (S)
46-48	77-81	Moderately Satisfactory (MS)
43-45	72-76	Less Satisfactory (LS)
41-42	68-71	Better than Passing (BTP)
40	67	Passing (P)
31-39	52-66	Below Passing (BP)
0-30	0-51	Failed (F)

In the pretest, both groups recorded mean scores within the "Failure" category—18.94 with an MPS of 31.56 for the non-Algodoo group and 22.00 with an MPS of 36.67 for the Algodoo group. An in-depth examination of the score distribution reveals the effects of the intervention. In the pretest, 100% of students in both groups scored in the "Failed" (F) category, indicating a lack of proficiency in Wave and Optics. However, in the posttest, the Algodoo simulations group demonstrated a noteworthy improvement in performance: 56% of students scored in the "Below Passing" (BP) range, 17% reached a "Less Satisfactory" (LS) level, and 6% each achieved the "Moderately Satisfactory" (MS), "Satisfactory" (S), and "Highly Satisfactory" (HS) levels. In contrast, the Laboratory Optics Kits group also showed improvement, but 63% of students remained in the "Below Passing" (BP) category, with 16% attaining "Highly Satisfactory" (HS), 11% at the "Satisfactory" (S) level, and only 5% in the "Moderately Satisfactory" (MS) range.

The pretest result reveals that students in both methods had minimal prior knowledge of Wave and Optics concepts. The uniformly low scores suggest a shared difficulty with the subject, which is known for its abstract and highly theoretical concepts. These findings align with Susac et al. (2024), who emphasized that students often struggle with core wave optics concepts due to their abstract and mathematical nature. This reinforces the idea that before any instructional intervention, students were equally unprepared to engage with the complex topics of Wave and Optics.

After the intervention, both groups showed enhanced academic performance. Algodoo group scores in the posttest increased to an average of 41.53 and an MPS of 69.22, categorized as "Better than Passing." In contrast, the non-Algodoo group attained a mean of 38.94 and an MPS of 64.90, categorized under the level of "Below Passing." The above improvement indicates that both teaching approaches—Algodoo simulations and Laboratory Optics Kits—helped improve the learners' understanding. As discussed by Badarudin et al. (2024), both conventional and virtual tools greatly enhanced physics learning performance. Likewise, Daaif et al. (2024) confirmed e-laboratory platforms as helpful alternatives or adjuncts to traditional means without jeopardizing academic quality.

Furthermore, even when both groups showed enhanced academic performance after the intervention, most students belonged to the "Below Passing" group. The enduring challenge may be explained by the fundamentally problematic nature of the subject matter of Wave and Optics. Theories like image formation by lenses and mirrors tend to be abstract and can be visualized only indirectly, most notably through conventional examination modes. Without tangible, dynamic visualizations, pupils might have trouble mentally visualizing how images form and consequently be limited in their conceptual grasp and performance levels. This challenge finds corroboration from

Aregehagn et al. (2023), who explained that learners tend to misinterpret these systems because of the abstractness of the material and the lack of good visual learning aids.

Another in-depth analysis above finds the Algodoo group showing a wider spread at higher proficiency levels. Specifically, 6% achieved at the "Highly Satisfactory" level and a further 6% at the "Satisfactory" level, compared to 16% and 11%, respectively, in the non-Algodoo group. Although the non-Algodoo group reported a slightly higher percentage at the HS level, the Algodoo group reported a better spread at all levels, reflecting a wider and consistent effect on student learning. This minimal advantage might be related to the interactive and visual nature of Algodoo simulations, which provide learners with the activation of variables in real-time and immediate feedback. This type of experiential learning corresponds with Sweller's Cognitive Load Theory (1988), which states that reducing unnecessary cognitive load—e.g., complex bench setups—enables learners to pay greater attention to conceptual understanding as they engage less time and effort in dealing with this kind of load. Kade et al. (2024) further corroborate this argument by mentioning that technologically driven simulations enhance conceptual mastery and minimize dependency on costly physical equipment.

Additionally, the success of both instructional approaches can be understood through Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory (1983), according to which experiential experience acquires prominence as a means through which individuals learn. The Algodoo simulations and Laboratory Optics Kits enabled the experiential learning cycle—concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. Herein, the learners used the tools to experience phenomena, reflect on the consequences, and progressively test their hypotheses to enhance conceptual insight in Wave and Optics.

Finally, the results indicate a blended method of teaching and learning utilizing both traditional and digital tools to achieve maximum academic success. As Bonifacio (2022) pointed out in the Philippine context, integrating physical manipulatives and digital simulations can enhance science education by engaging different learning styles and contexts. This validates the call for integrating both strategies since each lends a specific strength toward complementing the other: real-time interactivity through digital simulations and concrete, hands-on experience through traditional labs. Generally, the results demonstrate the advantage of employing a blended learning approach in teaching physics to foster a better comprehension of challenging physics concepts.

Level of Student's Retention Test in Wave and Optics

Table 2 reports performance levels on the retention test for those who used Algodoo simulations versus those who used Laboratory Optics Kits. Retention performance between the two groups differed according to the results. The Algodoo simulations group obtained a mean of 45.00, a "Better than Passing" level, reflecting an MPS of 68.33. The Laboratory Optics Kits group received a higher mean of 41.00, a "Less Satisfactory" level, reflecting an MPS of 75.00.

A look at the distribution of the scores highlights the differences in performance levels. In the Algodoo physics simulation class, 37% achieved a "Moderately Satisfactory" (MS), 26% were at the "Less Satisfactory" (LS), and 32% achieved a "Better than Passing" (BTP) level. The Laboratory Optics Kits class showed a varied distribution where at least 50% of the students were at the "Below Passing" (BP) level, 28% at the "Less Satisfactory" (LS) level, 11% at the "Better than Passing" (BTP) level, and a further 11% at the Satisfactory (S) level. It should also be noted that the two sets of students did not achieve any "Highly Satisfactory" (HS) or even higher performance levels. Generally speaking, the Algodoo simulations class did better than the Laboratory Optics Kits class.

Table 2. Retention Test Performance in Wave and Optics: Comparison Between Groups

Range Of Scores	Algodoo simulations Group		Laboratory Optics Kits Group		Level of Proficiency
	f	%	f	%	
59-60	0	0%	0	0%	E
55-58	0	0%	0	0%	VHS
52-54	0	0%	0	0%	HS
49-51	1	5%	2	11%	S
46-48	7	37%	0	0%	MS
43-45	5	26%	5	28%	LS
41-42	6	32%	2	11%	BTP
40	0	0%	0	0%	P
31-39	0	0%	9	50%	BP
0-30	0	0%	0	0%	F
Mean	45.00		41.00		
MPS	75.00 (MS)		68.33 (BTP)		

Legend:

Range of Grade	Grading Scale	Level of Proficiency
59-60	98-100	Excellent (E)
55-58	92-97	Very High Satisfactory (VHS)
52-54	87-91	Highly Satisfactory (HS)
49-51	82-86	Satisfactory (S)
46-48	77-81	Moderately Satisfactory (MS)
43-45	72-76	Less Satisfactory (LS)
41-42	68-71	Better than Passing (BTP)
40	67	Passing (P)
31-39	52-66	Below Passing (BP)
0-30	0-51	Failed (F)

The findings indicate that while both the Algodoo simulations and Laboratory Optics Kits effectively supported student retention of Wave and Optics concepts, the Algodoo group exhibited a significant advantage in retention performance. In particular, most of the Algodoo group attained a "Moderately Satisfactory" (MS) level, suggesting that students could significantly acquire and retain the intended learning competencies. In contrast, half of the students in the Laboratory Optics Kits group remained in the "Below Passing" (BP) category, highlighting a general lack of mastery in the subject following the intervention.

This difference in performance can be explained by the interactive and visually

dynamic nature of the Algodoo simulations and their self-paced mode. The software gave learners immediate feedback and manipulable variables through the drag-and-drop functionality and extensive parameters for adjustment. These interactive aspects probably resulted in a more engaging and intuitive learning experience conducive to enhanced conceptual understanding and enhanced memory retention. Additionally, the portability of Algodoo—run on low system requirements—enabled learners to perform the simulation after class time. This convenience may have benefited learners who needed more time to grasp abstract concepts in physics through independent self-paced practice at their convenience.

The higher retention rate found through Algodoo simulations has a basis in the theoretical foundations of education. As postulated by Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978), specifically the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), learners learn best when they are assisted in their learning zone through peer and instructor facilitation. The in-lab and virtual activities probably operated in learners' ZPD levels of facilitation through guided discovery and reinforcement. The higher retention rate found in the Algodoo group can also be supported by Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory (1985). The enhanced autonomy from virtual simulations allows for increased intrinsic motivation levels, which promote higher levels of engagement and eventually translate into better cognitive outcomes such as improved retention.

An expanding empirical base of research studies complements these findings. Kharki et al. (2021) indicated that learners utilizing virtual labs and theoretical teaching achieved better conceptual understanding and long-term retention. They stressed the benefits of self-paced virtual learning, where learners progress at their own pace according to their needs. This highlights the flexibility of Algodoo in allowing repeated exploration without time and space boundaries. Moreover, Gregorcic and Bodin (2017) and Rueda et al. (2014) indicated through their findings that virtual tools such as Algodoo address both visual and kinesthetic learners and enhance conceptual understanding and long-term retention. Kirmizigül (2021) also pointed out through study findings that Algodoo's interactive platform offers concrete experiences to learners, improving their concentration and retention results.

Validating this long-term effect, a longitudinal study conducted by Onorato et al. (2019) compared the dissemination of rolling motion concepts through Algodoo and found that students utilizing the simulation learned more about the concepts over three years compared to traditional teaching alone. All of these studies affirm the reality of the dynamic, interactive, and student-centered aspect of Algodoo simulations being key to superior physics education knowledge retention. Accordingly, Algodoo simulations can be employed to promote higher student retention.

Students' Engagement Level in Wave and Optics

The table below shows the students' engagement in the three sublevels: cognitive, behavioral, and affective. The data is derived from the students' engagement in Wave and Optics before and after exposure to the Algodoo and Laboratory Optics Kits.

Cognitive Engagement

The data in Table 3 illustrate the levels of cognitive engagement among students exposed to Algodoo simulations compared to those using Laboratory Optics Kits. In the pretest, the Laboratory Optics Kits group demonstrated a slightly higher initial engagement level, with a mean score of 3.56, classified as high engagement. In contrast, the Algodoo group recorded a mean of 3.35, indicating moderate engagement. After the intervention, both groups showed notable increases in engagement, with the non-Algodoo group reaching 4.08 and the Algodoo group closely behind at 4.03—both falling within the high engagement category.

Table 3. Students' Cognitive Engagement in Wave and Optics

Item	Algodoo simulations Group		Laboratory Optics Kits Group	
	Pretest \bar{x}	Posttest QD	Pretest \bar{x}	Posttest QD
Cognitive Engagement				
I appreciate and recognize the importance of mastering Wave and Optics concepts for my overall academic growth.	3.68	HE	4.42	HE
I actively seek to deepen my understanding of Wave and Optics by exploring advanced topics beyond the classroom.	3.68	HE	3.89	HE
When I miss class, I proactively consult with peers to grasp the concepts and complete activities I missed.	3.63	HE	4.37	HE
I put substantial effort into completing my coursework in Wave and Optics to ensure a deep grasp of the material.	3.42	ME	4.26	HE
I engage with Physics books and video lessons on Wave and Optics ahead of class to enhance my preparedness and comprehension.	3.32	ME	3.58	HE
I strive to maximize my learning in Wave and Optics by engaging with the material as thoroughly as possible.	3.31	ME	4.32	HE
I invest considerable effort in analyzing and understanding the procedures involved in our Wave and Optics lessons.	3.26	ME	3.95	HE
I have time to practice solving Wave and Optics problems after school	3.26	ME	3.74	HE
I dedicate significant time and effort to thoroughly understanding Wave and Optics lessons.	3.26	ME	4.16	HE

I use my free time to research additional information and resources on Wave and Optics to enrich my learning.	2.68	ME	3.63	HE	3.33	ME	3.56	HE
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OVERALL MEAN	3.35	ME	4.03	HE	3.56	HE	4.08	HE
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Legend:

Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Description
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Engagement (VHE)
3.51-4.50	Agree	High Engagement (HE)
2.51-3.50	Neutral	Moderate Engagement (ME)
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low Engagement (LE)
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Engagement (VLE)

A closer look at the pretest data identifies a variation in levels of engagement on various indicators for the two groups. Engagement herein was most significant in areas related to academic mastery and independent studying and lowest in independent research and problem-solving. The lowest mean rating of 2.68 on the question, "I use my free time to research additional information and resources on Wave and Optics to enrich my learning," was registered by the Algodoo group compared to a moderately higher score of 3.33 on the same question by the non-Algodoo group. This indicates that both sets of students initially demonstrated minimal initiative in studying course material independently. The level of independence in learning may be linked to the level of difficulty involved in the course, as noted by Sinkkonen and Tapani (2024). In contrast, the learners performed well through guided activities; they were bogged down when they were expected to independently interpret complex material, such as quantum mechanics or optics.

After intervention, both sets of respondents showed significant increases in all the measures of cognitive engagement. The maximum posttest mean in the Algodoo group on the statement, "I appreciate and recognize the importance of mastering Wave and Optics concepts for my overall academic growth," stood at 4.42. This was followed by extreme scores on statements of a proactive approach to learning and rich experience in working through the material. The non-Algodoo group also reported a maximum posttest score of 4.56 on two measurements: appreciation of academic development and commitment to studying, both very high engagement levels. The non-Algodoo group did experience a decline in a statement for independent exploration of advanced concepts from a level of 4.00 to 3.94.

The overall increase in mean scores—3.35 to 4.03 for the Algodoo group and 3.56 to 4.08 for the non-Algodoo group—indicates that both teaching modalities contributed positively to student engagement. While the non-Algodoo group maintained a slight edge in overall engagement, the Algodoo simulations group demonstrated comparable growth, particularly in aspects tied to autonomous and self-motivated learning. This suggests that Algodoo simulations and Laboratory Optics Kits promote independent learning. Supporting this is Çoramık & Ürek (2022), indicating that interactivity and visual feedback encourage independent inquiry and problem-solving by feeding on their curiosity to answer their questions.

Overall, these findings suggest that both traditional and digital instructional

methods can effectively enhance cognitive engagement but may differ in how they support specific dimensions of student learning. This pattern of results aligns with educational theories emphasizing experiential and self-directed learning. Dewey's Experiential Learning Theory (1986) supports the effectiveness of hands-on laboratory work in bridging theoretical content with real-world applications—evident in the non-Algodo group's high engagement in structured academic tasks. However, the decline in independent exploration among this group can be interpreted through Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (1978), which posits that while structured learning environments offer guided support, they may limit opportunities for autonomous inquiry—something simulations like Algodo are designed to promote.

Recent research supports these findings as well. Kade et al. (2024) established in their study that simulation-based learning, as in the case of Algodo, improves engagement through self-directed discovery, while conventionally conducted lab work promotes academic discipline. Likewise, Qin et al. (2025) established that both simulated and conventional laboratories improved cognitive engagement but varied in their facilitation of curiosity and mastery. Locally, Garcia (2020) proved that e-tivities and simulations could enhance cognitive engagement in physics, particularly conceptual comprehension and problem-solving. The study also asserted, however, the long-standing utility of structured laboratory work in developing disciplined academic engagement. These findings stress the importance of using a balanced instructional approach. Both digital simulations and traditional laboratory methods enhance student cognitive engagement. Hence, integrating both Algodo simulations and Laboratory Optics Kits based on the context in the classroom would further optimize instruction.

Behavioral Engagement

Table 4 presents the levels of behavioral engagement among students under the Algodo simulations and Laboratory Optics Kits group.

Table 4. Students' Behavioral Engagement in Wave and Optics

Item	Algodo simulations Group				Laboratory Optics Kits Group				
	Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest		
	\bar{x}	QD	\bar{x}	QD	\bar{x}	QD	\bar{x}	QD	
Behavioral Engagement									
I listen attentively to my teacher and classmates during presentations of outputs.	3.68	HE	4.32	HE	3.83	HE	4.61	VHE	
I contribute my ideas during group discussions in Wave and Optics class.	3.63	HE	4.32	HE	3.56	HE	4.28	HE	
I participate actively in group discussions during Wave and Optics class.	3.58	HE	4.21	HE	3.56	HE	4.61	VHE	
I take detailed notes during Wave and Optics class.	3.58	HE	4.11	HE	3.44	ME	4.44	HE	
I collaborate effectively with my	3.58	HE	4.53	VH	3.50	ME	4.67	VHE	

groupmates during Wave and Optics class.					E				
I actively participate in group activities during Wave and Optics class.	3.53	HE	4.26	HE	3.61	HE	4.56	VHE	
I raise my hand and ask questions whenever I need clarification about assignments in Wave and Optics class.	3.53	HE	3.89	HE	3.61	HE	4.17	HE	
I fulfill my assigned tasks during group discussions in Wave and Optics class.	3.47	ME	4.47	HE	3.44	ME	4.61	VHE	
I engage actively in various classroom activities in my Wave and Optics class.	3.37	ME	4.11	HE	3.22	ME	4.33	HE	
I diligently complete seat work assigned by the Physics teacher in class.	3.16	ME	4.21	HE	3.61	HE	4.33	HE	
OVERALL MEAN	3.51	HE	4.24	HE	3.54	HE	4.46	VHE	

Legend:

Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Description
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Engagement (VHE)
3.51-4.50	Agree	High Engagement (HE)
2.51-3.50	Neutral	Moderate Engagement (ME)
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low Engagement (LE)
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Engagement (VLE)

In the pretest, both groups already demonstrated high behavioral engagement, with the Algodoo group posting a mean score of 3.51 and the non-Algodoo group slightly higher at 3.54. Notably, both groups experienced significant improvements in their posttest results. The Algodoo group increased to a mean of 4.24, sustaining its position within the high engagement category, while the non-Algodoo group achieved a mean of 4.46, indicating very high behavioral engagement. A closer analysis of the pretest results reveals that the lowest behavioral engagement scores in the Algodoo group were related to diligence in completing seatwork, having a mean value of 3.16, active classroom participation with a mean of 3.37, and fulfilling group tasks with a value of 3.47. Similarly, the non-Algodoo group also scored relatively low in areas such as active classroom participation, with a mean score of 3.22, detailed note-taking having a value of 3.44, and group task fulfillment, with a mean of 3.44. These initial values suggest that prior to the intervention, students in both groups engaged moderately well in class-related behaviors. However, they still had room for improvement in routine and collaborative activities.

Post-intervention, the highest behavioral engagement scores in the Algodoo group were observed in indicators related to collaboration and attentiveness. Specifically, the item *"I collaborate effectively with my groupmates during Wave and Optics class"* recorded a high mean of 4.53, followed by equally strong scores for *"I contribute my ideas during group discussions"* and *"I listen attentively to my teacher and classmates,"* both at 4.32. In comparison, the non-Algodoo group registered its highest posttest scores in the same collaborative and attentiveness indicators, with values ranging from 4.61 to 4.67, which qualified as Very High Engagement. This pattern reflects a more substantial behavioral improvement in the non-Algodoo group across a broader set of classroom

activities, particularly in listening, collaboration, and fulfilling group responsibilities.

These findings suggest that while both instructional methods fostered behavioral engagement, the traditional laboratory group demonstrated stronger gains across multiple domains. The non-Algodo group notably excelled in attentiveness and collaborative behavior, possibly due to the need for real-time verbal communication and coordination when handling physical laboratory equipment. Interestingly, the most substantial improvement in the Algodo group was in completing seatwork, indicating that digital simulations may encourage students to focus more on completing assigned tasks independently during class time. These results suggest that traditional labs foster explicit engagement behaviors such as active discussion and note-taking, while simulations support focus and independence in task completion. The variation in improvement patterns may also reflect the differing features of each method—real-world manipulation versus interactive visualization.

These results are also explained well by Skinner's Operant Conditioning theory (1938), which states that reinforcement from real-life cues can enhance wanted behavior. During traditional lab work, the students directly manipulated objects such as light sources and opaque materials, reinforcing participation through sensory experience and visible results. The general rise in participation levels between both groups is also explained by Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977), where the dynamics of peer interaction and modeling enhance collaboration and participation. The findings indicate that simulated and real settings can promote participation, especially when designed to facilitate interaction and responsibility in a task.

Numerous recent studies support these insights. Yeni et al. (2024) and Kota (2024) concluded that interactive simulations enhance behavioral engagement by promoting active problem-solving, collaboration, and exploration. However, they also noted that traditional lab practices result in more explicit participation and attentiveness, especially in group settings requiring communication about equipment use. Locally, Cezar et al. (2021) emphasized that simulations foster independent task completion and collaborative interaction, but traditional labs are more effective in developing note-taking habits and focused listening. These findings support the integration of blended learning environments that combine the strengths of both instructional approaches. Thus, by utilizing both real-world and digital tools, educators can optimize behavioral engagement, enhance student motivation, and promote deeper conceptual understanding in physics education.

Affective Engagement

Table 5 shows the levels of affective engagement among students exposed to Algodo simulations compared to those in the Laboratory Optics Kits group. The pretest scores indicate both groups previously had high affective engagement, and the Algodo group had a slightly higher mean score of 3.69 compared to a mean of 3.68 for the non-Algodo group. These observations indicate that before the intervention, both groups of learners already had a positive emotional attachment toward their physics topic, namely

Wave and Optics. The same observations align with Laine et al. (2020), demonstrating that learners' emotional attachment results from their interest and curiosity, which were already aroused through personalized contexts.

Both groups showed a significant boost in affective engagement following the intervention. The Algodoo group achieved a posttest mean of 4.42 and a high level of engagement, whereas the non-Algodoo group achieved a posttest mean of 4.53 and a very high level. These increases highlight that both teaching methods enhanced students' emotional participation in the subject matter. Both groups achieved their most excellent scores on pretest items related to satisfaction and motivation. The statement *"I find satisfaction reflecting on the lessons from Wave and Optics after class"* achieved a pretest mean of 3.84 and 3.78 for the Algodoo and non-Algodoo groups, respectively. Conversely, the lowest engagement was noted in the teacher and peer support-related statements. The lowest pretest score achieved by the non-Algodoo group at 3.50 came from the statement, *"I appreciate the positive reinforcement from my Wave and Optics teacher, which makes me participate in class,"* demonstrating low affective engagement.

Table 5. Students' Affective Engagement in Wave and Optics

Item	Algodoo simulations Group				Laboratory Optics Kits Group					
	Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest			
	\bar{x}	QD	\bar{x}	QD	\bar{x}	QD	\bar{x}	QD		
Affective Engagement										
I find satisfaction in reflecting on the lessons from Wave and Optics after class.	3.84	HE	4.37	HE	3.78	HE	4.39	HE		
I enjoy the sense of accomplishment I feel when completing activities in my Wave and Optics class.	3.79	HE	4.53	VHE	3.56	HE	4.61	VHE		
I appreciate the encouragement from my Wave and Optics teacher, which makes me feel more involved in class.	3.74	HE	4.47	HE	3.50	ME	4.67	VHE		
I feel pleased working collaboratively with my groupmates during Wave and Optics class.	3.74	HE	4.26	HE	3.67	HE	4.67	VHE		
I am motivated to attend every Wave and Optics class to maximize my learning experience.	3.74	HE	4.32	HE	3.78	HE	4.00	HE		
I feel reassured by my Physics teacher's efforts to help me learn effectively.	3.63	HE	4.47	HE	3.78	HE	4.78	VHE		
I am grateful for the support from my classmates, which positively impacts my engagement with Wave and Optics activities.	3.63	HE	4.47	HE	3.61	HE	4.72	VHE		

I look forward to participating in the group activities during my Wave and Optics class.	3.63	HE	4.37	HE	3.83	HE	4.61	VHE
I feel engaged and interested throughout my Wave and Optics class.	3.58	HE	4.47	HE	3.56	HE	4.44	HE
I derive enjoyment from the various activities conducted in my Wave and Optics class.	3.53	HE	4.42	HE	3.72	HE	4.44	HE
OVERALL MEAN	3.69	HE	4.42	HE	3.68	HE	4.53	VHE

Legend:

Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Description
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Engagement (VHE)
3.51-4.50	Agree	High Engagement (HE)
2.51-3.50	Neutral	Moderate Engagement (ME)
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low Engagement (LE)
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Engagement (VLE)

Post-intervention, the Algodoo group showed strong improvements in all affective engagement indicators. The highest posttest scores were recorded in *"I enjoy the sense of accomplishment I feel when completing activities,"* with a score of 4.53, and *"I feel reassured by my Physics teacher's efforts to help me learn effectively,"* at 4.47. Likewise, the non-Algodoo group posted its highest scores in similar indicators—4.78 and 4.67, respectively—both categorized as very high engagement. Notably, the non-Algodoo group outperformed the Algodoo group in teacher and peer support, suggesting that face-to-face lab activities may promote stronger interpersonal bonds and encouragement. Overall, the non-Algodoo group's affective engagement increased from 3.68 to 4.53, while the Algodoo group increased from 3.69 to 4.42. These results imply that while both instructional strategies enhance emotional investment in learning, traditional laboratory activities have a slightly stronger impact.

These results indicate that simulation-based and traditional laboratory methodologies are beneficial in promoting affective engagement in physics instruction. The progress observed in the Algodoo group can be explained by the exploratory and autonomous nature of the simulations, which makes it possible for learners to visualize concepts dynamically and experience a sense of autonomy. The slightly better progress found in the non-Algodoo group indicates that hands-on experience creates a more satisfying emotional experience through tangible interaction, real application in the real world, and instant feedback from a teacher. Herein lies the communication-reinforcement cycle—teacher reinforcement and peer communication, which prevails in traditional labs. Accordingly, whereas digital simulations enhance motivation through interactive visualizations, actual labs encourage enhanced emotional engagement through interactive and supportive experiences. A dual-mode approach combining both methods may maximize affective engagement by tapping the strengths of exploratory experience and supportive communication in a single package.

These findings are aligned with Deci and Ryan's (1985) Self-Determination Theory, highlighting the central role of competence and relatedness in promoting intrinsic

motivation. Both approaches seem to satisfy those psychological needs and thus promote a stronger emotional attachment to the subject among the learners. As seen through observations when creating diagrams, students carrying on discussions in lesson group chats demonstrate how both methods promote participation outside the classroom. Fredricks et al. (2004) also suggest that affective engagement arises when learners become emotionally engaged in interactive and inquisitive activities since both simulation and lab-learning settings promote those aspects. Empirical research substantiates these results. Kade et al. (2024) indicated that simulations produce high affective engagement through their interactive and dynamic nature. Zuccarini et al. (2024) also found that simulations enhance motivation and interest through immediate visualization and feedback provision. Both studies also indicated that although less dynamic, traditional laboratory lessons tend to produce stronger emotional involvement through the interactive nature of the learning and immediate instructor feedback.

In the Philippine context, Cezar et al. (2021) revealed that computer-supported simulations were highly effective in eliciting enjoyment and satisfaction. In contrast, however, Tagupa et al. (2024) pointed out that learners involved in conventional laboratory sessions showed increased affective engagement as they valued teacher interaction and experience. These findings promote combining both to develop a stronger emotional bond between science and learners.

Summary of Students' Engagement in Wave and Optics

Table 6 summarizes student engagement across cognitive, behavioral, and affective domains before and after the intervention period for both the Algodoo and non-Algodoo simulation groups.

Table 6. Summary of Students' Engagement in Wave and Optics

Engagement Level	Algodoo simulations Group				Laboratory Optics Kits Group			
	Pretest		Posttest		Posttest			
	\bar{x}	QD	\bar{x}	QD	\bar{x}	QD	\bar{x}	QD
Cognitive Engagement	3.35	ME	4.03	HE	3.56	HE	4.08	HE
Behavioral Engagement	3.51	HE	4.24	HE	3.54	HE	4.46	VHE
Affective Engagement	3.69	HE	4.42	HE	3.68	HE	4.53	VHE
OVERALL MEAN	3.52	HE	4.23	HE	3.59	HE	4.36	HE

Legend:

Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Description
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Engagement (VHE)
3.51-4.50	Agree	High Engagement (HE)
2.51-3.50	Neutral	Moderate Engagement (ME)
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low Engagement (LE)
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Engagement (VLE)

Both groups showed a higher level of overall engagement after the intervention. The Algodoo simulations shifted from 3.52 on the pretest to 4.23, and the Laboratory

Optics Kits group increased from 3.59 to 4.36. Both scores lie in the high engagement level. These results indicate that both instructional approaches successfully improved students' engagement in studying Wave and Optics, although the non-Algodoo group showed a slightly better improvement.

Cognitive involvement in the Algodoo simulations group improved from 3.35 (moderate involvement) to 4.03 (high involvement), reflecting greater engagement in autonomous learning and conceptual exploration. The simulations likely stimulated intellectual curiosity, allowing students to dynamically manipulate variables and visualize physical phenomena. The non-Algodoo group also showed cognitive gains, increasing from 3.56 to 4.08, maintaining a high level of engagement. This minor difference in posttest scores suggests that traditional laboratory methods might offer more reinforcement of theoretical concepts through tangible, real-world experimentation.

Both groups saw considerable improvements in behavioral engagement. The Algodoo group rose from 3.51 to 4.24, both classified as high engagement. The platform's interactive design allowed students to participate actively in discussions and collaborative activities, boosting classroom involvement. Meanwhile, the non-Algodoo group demonstrated an even more significant increase, rising from 3.54 to 4.46, reaching a very high engagement level. The nature of laboratory work encouraged active involvement through collaboration with peers and instructor guidance, ensuring consistency and discipline in task execution.

Affective engagement showed the most significant increases in both groups. The Algodoo group improved from 3.69 to 4.42, demonstrating sustained high engagement. The ability to explore and manipulate simulations likely contributed to greater emotional involvement and motivation. The non-Algodoo group, however, showed an even larger increase—from 3.68 to 4.53—reaching a very high level of affective engagement. The hands-on experiences, face-to-face interactions, and immediate feedback from the instructor likely provided a more emotionally supportive environment, fostering a stronger emotional connection to the subject.

While all dimensions of engagement improved following the intervention, it is worth noting that affective engagement showed the highest increase, whereas cognitive engagement exhibited the least growth. This pattern suggests that students responded more strongly on an emotional level than on a deep intellectual one. The immersive, interactive nature of both instructional approaches, especially the collaborative and sensory-rich environment of traditional laboratories and the novelty and autonomy offered by Algodoo simulations, likely promoted greater emotional connection, enjoyment, and deeper appreciation of the Wave and Optics course. Factors such as peer interaction, real-time feedback from the instructor, and the satisfaction of manipulating physics or digital elements contributed to heightened enthusiasm and a sense of belonging in the learning experience.

In contrast, the lesser extent of improvement in cognitive engagement may simply be a function of the inherent difficulties of physics as a complex subject matter. Cognitive

engagement entails interest and the capacity to internalize abstract concepts, persist under challenge, and apply learned material independently—capabilities that may be slower to establish than affective responses. This result points to a key pedagogical insight: Emotion can be easily triggered by an engaging experience, but cognitive engagement takes intentional instructional design, extended practice, and perhaps other supporting scaffolding to engender deepening and autonomous learning habits.

Overall, both pedagogical approaches enhanced student engagement in all facets. Yet, the non-Algodoos group reported consistently better posttest scores, especially on behavior and emotion, indicating that conventional lab approaches tend to encourage greater interpersonal engagement and emotional investment.

These results emphasize the essential role of hands-on science laboratory experience in promoting motivated student engagement, cooperation, and affective involvement in the learning experience. The sensory, interactive, and tangible qualities of the traditional hands-on labs and immediate instructor and peer interaction enhance a more engaging and emotionally satisfying educational experience. At the same time, simulation instruction adds significantly to cognitive participation and promotes independence through discovery learning. These findings suggest a mixed-mode instructional solution—combining simulated experience and hands-on wet labs—may optimize engagement by enabling the conceptualization of abstract concepts and a form of interpersonal interaction and application in a real-life context.

Numerous recent studies support this view. Tagupa et al. (2024) reported that learners involved in hands-on physics labs displayed increased levels of engagement through their actual manipulation of equipment and interaction with peers. Zakariya (2024) reported that conventional laboratories boost motivation and conceptualization by basing abstract theory on tangible experiences. In addition, Pranata (2024) stressed the superiority of blended learning strategies in stating that the alignment of simulations and laboratories harnesses the advantages of both modalities—simulation facilitating self-paced discovery and visualization and laboratories reinforcing attainment through tangible manipulation and interaction with peers. Therefore, a blended strategy combining simulations and conventional laboratories maximizes cognitive, behavioral, and affective engagement by reconciling the benefits of autonomous exploration and tangible, collaborative learning.

Comparison of the Level of Academic Performance

Table 7 displays the results of the Mann-Whitney U test conducted to compare the academic performance of students exposed to Algodoos simulations and those taught using Laboratory Optics Kits. The test aimed to assess whether the differences in pretest and posttest scores between the two groups were statistically significant. Comparison of pretest results using the Mann-Whitney U test yielded a value of 0.029, indicating a statistically significant difference between the groups' pretest scores. This suggests that students in the Algodoos group started with a higher level of understanding. In the posttest, the Mann-Whitney U test produced a p-value of 0.454, indicating no statistically significant

difference between the two groups' academic performance after the intervention.

Table 7. Mann-Whitney U Test: Comparison of Students' Academic Performance

Type of Test	Group	Sum of Ranks (S)	Mean Rank (MR)	Z	P-value
Posttest	Algodoo simulations	385.50	20.29	-0.748	0.454
	Laboratory Optics Kits	317.50	17.64		
Pretest	Algodoo simulations	432.50	22.76	-2.179	0.029
	Laboratory Optics Kits	270.50	15.03		

Legend: **significant at 0.05 level

The significant pretest difference implies that the Algodoo group entered the study with a higher baseline understanding than the Laboratory Optics Kits group, which may be attributed to prior knowledge, learning preferences, or familiarity with simulation-based tools. However, this advantage did not persist post-intervention, as indicated by the non-significant posttest results. This suggests that both instructional strategies—Algodoo simulations and traditional laboratory experiments—were equally effective in enhancing academic performance on Wave and Optics concepts. Although the Algodoo group had a slightly higher posttest sum of ranks, the lack of statistical significance implies that the difference was not meaningful in educational terms. This further supports the idea that both methods facilitated learning gains, potentially offering different but equally effective learning methods.

These findings reflect established educational theories and current research. Vygotsky's (1978) Social Constructivist Theory suggests that students with earlier exposure to interactive tools—such as simulations—may benefit from better cognitive scaffolding, explaining the initial advantage of the Algodoo group. However, Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory (1983) posits that learning occurs through active experience, which both the digital and traditional groups received, resulting in comparable posttest outcomes. Sweller's Cognitive Load Theory (1988) further supports this, proposing that simulations and hands-on activities can effectively manage cognitive demands if designed appropriately, leading to similar learning outcomes.

Empirical studies back these theoretical insights. Kade et al. (2024) demonstrated that simulations improve students' visualization and understanding of abstract physics concepts. Similarly, Daaif et al. (2024) showed that both virtual and physical laboratory methods produce comparable learning gains when structured engagement is provided. Within the Philippine context, Bonifacio (2022) reported that both traditional and technology-enhanced physics instruction improved student engagement and knowledge retention. Hinampas et al. (2018) emphasized that a blended approach combining both methods results in the most comprehensive conceptual mastery. These findings affirm the current study's results, supporting the use of both instructional strategies in promoting

effective and engaging physics education.

Comparison of Student’s Retention Test in Both Groups

Table 8 presents the results of the Mann-Whitney U test, which compares the retention test scores of students in Wave and Optics between those who utilized Algodoo simulations and those who participated in non-Algodoo simulation activities. The analysis aimed to determine whether there was a statistically significant difference in retention scores between the two groups. As shown in the table, The Mann-Whitney U test yielded a p-value of 0.006.

Table 8. Mann-Whitney U Test: Comparison of Retention Test Performance in Wave and Optics

Type of Test	Group	Sum of Ranks (S)	Mean Rank (MR)	Z	P-value
Retention Test	Algodoo simulations	425.50	22.39	-1.982	0.006
	Laboratory Optics Kits	277.50	15.42		

Legend: **significant at 0.05 level

The results display a diverse performance related to retention between the two groups, as presented through the p-value of 0.006. The outcome calls for the null hypothesis to be rejected as it affirms that students who used Algodoo simulations performed better on retention than those who utilized Laboratory Optics Kits. The result indicates that the interactive and self-paced visual learning platform presented through Algodoo simulations efficiently supported long-term memory of concepts related to Waves and Optics. This could be explained through Algodoo simulations, as they were easily accessible, and the lessons could be applied at any time.

These results identify the value of Algodoo simulations in promoting better student retention over actual laboratory equipment. The convenience and setup ease of Algodoo simulations potentially enabled autonomous learning by the students, providing added avenues for applying theoretical concepts in real-life contexts in a simulated situation. This interactive and immersive pedagogy would also likely account for improved remembrance of concepts about Waves and Optics when compared with the method used by the non-Algodoo group in a traditional laboratory setting. The non-Algodoo group also showed improved retention levels, potentially because of hands-on, experiential exposure to physical materials that supported learning through actual experimentation.

The improvements in retention, as observed, correspond to the Constructivist Learning Theory in which active construction of knowledge through experience and exploration is stressed (Piaget, 1952; Vygotsky, 1978). Algodoo simulations can be a proper scaffolding mechanism since they enable learners to test hypotheses, visualize abstract ideas, and obtain immediate feedback, improving long-term retention. Both instructional approaches also conform to Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory (1983),

given that learners in both groups conducted active experiences with concepts related to Waves and Optics, manipulated variables, and developed their conceptual level of understanding, enhancing the outcome of retention.

Additionally, earlier research has established the capacity of digital simulations to foster conceptual understanding and retention. Nkwande (2024) concluded that virtual labs like Algodoo enhance student retention through a self-paced and interactive form of learning where learners can continually rehearse experiments and interact meaningfully with the material. Likewise, Alkan et al. (2024) and Antonio and Castro (2023) noted that virtual simulations yield statistically higher long-term retention than conventional approaches.

Whereas the Algodoo group provided a considerable advantage in retention, the findings also indicate the merit of the non-Algodoo group's experiential, hands-on experience through Laboratory Optics Kits. Both approaches yielded positive outcomes in retention and thus affirm the imperative of a mixed-learning approach combining computer simulations and hands-on experimentation. Banda and Nzabahimana (2021) provide a supporting argument in line with this approach by noting that a mix of virtual and hands-on experiments resulted in better conceptual understanding and better retention. Likewise, Mihret et al. (2022) indicated that learners who showed hybrid instructional methods acquired better problem-solving skills and enhanced confidence in applying physics concepts in real-life application contexts. The findings generally affirm the better long-term knowledge acquisition by digital simulations than conventional means of laboratories through Wave and Optics.

Comparison of Student's Level of Engagement

Table 9 presents the student engagement levels for two instructional methods: Algodoo simulations and Laboratory Optics Kits using the Laboratory Optics Kits.

Table 9. Mann-Whitney U Test: Comparison of Students' Engagement

Type of Test	Group	Sum of Ranks (S)	Mean Rank (MR)	Z	P-value
Posttest	Algodoo simulations	17.21	327.00	-1.034	0.301
	Laboratory Optics Kits	20.89	376.00		
Pretest	Algodoo simulations	18.37	349.00	-0.365	0.715
	Laboratory Optics Kits	19.67	354.00		

Legend: **significant at 0.05 level

The analysis focused on whether or not the difference in engagement between the two groups would be statistically significant. In the pretest, the Mann-Whitney U test gave a p-value of 0.715 and a non-statistically significant difference between the two groups'

initial level of engagement. Likewise, the Mann-Whitney U test of posttests gave a p-value of 0.301 and a non-statistically significant difference between the two groups' engagement after the intervention.

These findings indicate that both pedagogical methods—digital simulations and conventional laboratory settings—were similarly effective in engaging students in the cognitive, affective, and behavioral realms. The high level of engagement realized in both conditions can be linked to the hands-on and investigative nature of the activities, which allowed students to see abstract concepts and interact with peers in ways they could not otherwise in a traditional classroom and also obtain immediate feedback from the instructor. As Experiential Learning Theory, advanced by Kolb (1983), illustrates, learning will be greatest when learners engage in a cycle of concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. The Algodoo simulation and traditional optics kit met those conditions, offering rich contexts to build understanding through actual or virtual manipulation of variables and experimentation.

The lack of a considerable difference in engagement after intervention indicates that the learners were as motivated and engaged under both teaching modes. This finding confirms Piaget's (1952) constructivist theory, whereby learners construct knowledge through meaningful interaction with their surroundings. Whether through physical devices or virtual models, learners got a chance to probe, predict, and infer—primary procedures engaged in toward enhanced cognitive participation.

Supporting studies affirm the above findings. Ates and Koroğlu (2024), for example, and Kharki et al. (2021) both stressed the capacity of traditional and computer tools to engage pupils if used sensibly. Additionally, Kapici et al. (2019) also claimed that combining hands-on and virtual labs in sequence produces superior student results compared to their solitary utilization. Similarly, Schnieder et al. (2022) identified flexibility and variety in experience as valued by students from a blended approach. Hence, engagement can be maximized by harnessing the benefits of both forms.

The findings justify using traditional labs and computer simulations in science instruction. While Algodoo's immediate feedback and visual appeal might capture today's digital-native learners' interest, traditional labs will remain crucial in developing manual dexterity and reinforcing core science concepts. Bonifacio (2022) emphasized that a mixed approach combining the two methods can better address the diverse needs of learners and enhance general interest and education in physics.

Conclusions

Findings showed that both methods effectively enhanced conceptual understanding. Regarding retention, the Algodoo group outperformed the non-Algodoo group, suggesting that digital simulations' interactive and self-paced nature supports long-term learning.

Both the Algodoo simulations and Laboratory Optics Kits effectively improved students' cognitive, behavioral, and affective engagement. While both methods promoted active learning, the non-Algodoo group showed slightly greater gains in behavioral and affective engagement, possibly due to more interpersonal interaction during hands-on activities.

No significant difference was found in academic performance between the Algodoo and non-Algodoo groups, indicating that both methods are equally effective in improving understanding of Wave and Optics concepts. Findings suggest that using both or either supports student learning. However, there was a significant difference in retention levels, with the Algodoo group demonstrating better long-term understanding. This implies that digital simulations may offer an advantage in knowledge retention due to their flexibility and interactive features.

Despite improved engagement in both groups, there was no significant difference in engagement levels between them. This shows that both digital and traditional methods are effective in fostering student engagement and can be flexibly used to address various learning needs.

Recommendations

Teachers may integrate Algodoo simulations and traditional Laboratory Optics Kits, as both methods have improved students' academic performance. A blended approach using Algodoo simulations and Laboratory Optics Kits is recommended—Lab Kits for face-to-face sessions to enhance hands-on learning, and Algodoo for online, self-paced activities. Given the higher retention rates in the Algodoo group, digital simulations may be used asynchronously by students to support long-term retention of concepts in Wave and Optics.

As both methods enhanced engagement, schools may support teaching strategies that combine digital and traditional approaches, particularly for universities with Hyflex modalities utilizing both online and face-to-face instruction. Traditional labs may foster affective and behavioral engagement better, while Algodoo simulations strengthen cognitive engagement.

Since no significant differences were found in the two groups' academic performance and engagement, Algodoo simulations and Laboratory Optics Kits may be considered equally effective. Policymakers may promote instructional flexibility by endorsing curriculum designs that incorporate both.

Future researchers may conduct longitudinal studies with larger sample sizes to assess long-term impacts on performance, retention, and engagement. Future research may also isolate the effect of Algodoo simulations versus purely traditional instruction to refine instructional recommendations.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research conformed to ethical guidelines established by the Institutional Ethics Review Committee (IERC) of Central Mindanao University. Participants provided informed consent and were free to withdraw without consequences. Anonymity and confidentiality were upheld at all times according to the Data Privacy Act of 2012. No conflict of interest occurred, and plagiarism was not committed. Results were objectively reported for purposes of research only.

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